

Excess molar volumes and viscosities of binary liquid mixtures of 1-propanol + ethylene glycol monomethyl ether, + diethylene glycol monomethyl ether, and + triethylene glycol monomethyl ether at (298.15, 308.15 and 318.15) K

Amalendu Pal* and Anil Kumar

Department of Chemistry, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra-136 119, India

E-mail : search@vidya.kuru.ernet.in Fax : 91-1744-238277

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Excess molar volume V_m^E and viscosity η have been measured as a function of composition for binary liquids mixtures of 1-propanol (C_3H_7OH) with ethylene glycol monomethyl ether (2-methoxyethanol), $CH_3(OC_2H_4)OH$, diethylene glycol monomethyl ether (2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethanol), $CH_3(OC_2H_4)_2OH$ and triethylene glycol monomethyl ether (2-(2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethoxy)ethanol), $CH_3(OC_2H_4)_3OH$, at 308.15 and 318.15 K and atmospheric pressure. Measurements of excess molar volume and viscosity at 298.15 K for the mixtures 1-propanol + triethylene glycol monomethyl ether (2-(2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethoxy)ethanol), $CH_3(OC_2H_4)_3OH$ and viscosity at 298.15 K for the mixtures 1-propanol + diethyleneglycol monomethyl ether (2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethanol), $CH_3(OC_2H_4)_2OH$ have also been made over the whole composition range. From the experimental data, the deviation in viscosity η from $\sum x_i\eta_i$ have been calculated at various temperatures. Both excess molar volumes and viscosity deviations are fitted to Redlich-Kister type polynomial equation to estimate the binary coefficient and standard errors. The experimental and calculated quantities were used to analyze the mixing behavior of the components. McAllister's three-body and four-body interaction models were used to correlate the kinematic viscosities. Furthermore, activation enthalpies, ΔH^* and entropies, ΔS^* , of viscous flow were evaluated and their variation with concentration is discussed.

As a part of our systemic studies on thermodynamic, transport, and acoustic properties of mixtures containing *n*-alkoxyethanols, we have recently reported excess molar volumes, speeds of sound, and viscosities of binary liquids mixtures of *n*-alkoxyethanols with toluene¹, alkylacetates^{2,3}, and dialkylcarbonates⁴. A few studies involving binary alkoxyethanols with amine and alcohol systems have been carried out^{5,6} in our laboratory with the aim of a better understanding about association behavior of the amine or alcohol and the ether at 298.15 K. These investigations were concerned with the sensitivity to the alkyl chain length as well as the polar head group of the composition dependence of a variety of thermodynamic properties and functions. In continuation of these investigations on the thermodynamic and transport properties of some binary mixtures containing *n*-alkoxyethanols, the present paper reports the excess molar volume V_m^E and viscosity η for binary mixtures of 1-propanol (C_3H_7OH), with ethylene glycol monomethyl ether ($CH_3(OC_2H_4)OH$) and diethylene glycol monomethyl ether ($CH_3(OC_2H_4)_2OH$), over the whole composition range at 308.15 and 318.15 K and at atmospheric pressure, for characterizing their possible interactions. We have also measured the viscosity of 1-propanol (C_3H_7OH) with diethylene

glycol monomethyl ether ($CH_3(OC_2H_4)_2OH$) at 298.15 K and excess molar volume and viscosity of 1-propanol (C_3H_7OH) with triethylene glycol monomethyl ether ($CH_3(OC_2H_4)_3OH$) at 298.15, 308.15 and 318.15 K. The excess molar volumes at 298.15 K for 1-propanol with ethylene glycol monomethyl ether and diethylene glycol monomethyl ether and viscosities for 1-propanol with ethylene glycol monomethyl ether at 298.15 K have been reported in our earlier papers^{7,8}. Following these results, isobaric thermal expansivities α at 308.15 K and atmospheric pressure are reported. The study will be useful in developing a further complete treatment of the present mixtures. The present study was therefore undertaken in order to study the effect of temperature and of specific interactions on the excess properties, the influence of the enlargement of the polar head group of the alkoxyethanol by the addition of an OC_2H_4 unit, for species with a common alkyl group.

Results and discussion

Tables 1 and 2 give the experimental results of the excess molar volumes and viscosities for all the mixtures as a function of mole fraction and temperature. The measured

Table 1. Excess molar volumes, V_m^E , of the binary mixtures at various temperatures

x_1	$V_m^E \times 10^6$ ($m^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	x_1	$V_m^E \times 10^6$ ($m^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	x_1	$V_m^E \times 10^6$ ($m^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
CH₃(OC₂H₄)OH (1) + C₃H₇OH (2)					
308.15 K					
0.0141	0.006	0.4091	0.066	0.5948	0.064
0.0577	0.019	0.4214	0.066	0.6105	0.063
0.1096	0.033	0.4401	0.066	0.6391	0.062
0.1707	0.042	0.4532	0.066	0.6529	0.059
0.2471	0.053	0.4734	0.067	0.7112	0.051
0.3160	0.059	0.5055	0.067	0.7974	0.038
0.3442	0.062	0.5085	0.067	0.8649	0.028
0.3681	0.064	0.5423	0.065	0.9119	0.019
0.3725	0.062	0.5506	0.065	0.9657	0.003
0.3897	0.065	0.5875	0.064		
318.15 K					
0.0219	0.007	0.4333	0.077	0.6055	0.070
0.0452	0.011	0.4405	0.077	0.6413	0.065
0.0867	0.025	0.4652	0.076	0.6920	0.059
0.1085	0.031	0.4882	0.076	0.7522	0.049
0.1490	0.041	0.5027	0.076	0.8194	0.040
0.1986	0.047	0.5137	0.076	0.8581	0.034
0.2584	0.060	0.5247	0.074	0.8894	0.028
0.3329	0.069	0.5454	0.074	0.9233	0.023
0.3584	0.071	0.5564	0.073	0.9473	0.017
0.3812	0.074	0.5639	0.073	0.9752	0.010
0.3875	0.075	0.5866	0.071		
0.4091	0.075	0.6004	0.070		
CH₃(OC₂H₄)₂OH (1) + C₃H₇OH (2)					
308.15 K					
0.0102	-0.002	0.2836	-0.017	0.5013	-0.024
0.0343	-0.003	0.3001	-0.019	0.5648	-0.021
0.0706	-0.007	0.3238	-0.018	0.6365	-0.020
0.1076	-0.009	0.3295	-0.019	0.6818	-0.018
0.1461	-0.012	0.3557	-0.020	0.7497	-0.018
0.1869	-0.012	0.3772	-0.022	0.8025	-0.020
0.2364	-0.012	0.3811	-0.022	0.8879	-0.019
0.2601	-0.014	0.4106	-0.023	0.9385	-0.015
0.2770	-0.017	0.4589	-0.024		
318.15 K					
0.0104	-0.001	0.3304	-0.005	0.5070	-0.007
0.0324	0.006	0.3360	-0.004	0.5450	-0.005
0.0495	0.007	0.3616	-0.006	0.5658	-0.005
0.0906	0.002	0.3746	-0.007	0.6311	-0.008
0.1196	-0.003	0.3948	-0.010	0.7094	-0.006
0.1577	-0.009	0.4087	-0.010	0.7831	-0.008

Table-1 (contd.)

0.2002	-0.009	0.4381	-0.012	0.8564	-0.003
0.2405	-0.009	0.4398	-0.010	0.9046	-0.002
0.2853	-0.008	0.4706	-0.010	0.9418	0.002
0.2941	-0.009	0.4883	-0.009	0.9858	0.001
0.3054	-0.006	0.4936	-0.010		
CH₃(OC₂H₄)₃OH (1) + C₃H₇OH (2)					
298.15 K					
0.0044	-0.005	0.2729	-0.121	0.4710	-0.124
0.0199	-0.023	0.3058	-0.122	0.5455	-0.112
0.0460	-0.041	0.3350	-0.123	0.6570	-0.089
0.0760	-0.068	0.3551	-0.128	0.7211	-0.077
0.1130	-0.080	0.3586	-0.126	0.7909	-0.059
0.1497	-0.093	0.3964	-0.128	0.8574	-0.036
0.1785	-0.109	0.4080	-0.127	0.9050	-0.025
0.2336	-0.117	0.4137	-0.127	0.9632	-0.020
308.15 K					
0.0045	-0.006	0.2380	-0.114	0.4457	-0.134
0.0157	-0.017	0.2559	-0.117	0.5156	-0.126
0.0351	-0.033	0.2584	-0.118	0.5933	-0.117
0.0691	-0.057	0.2868	-0.120	0.6728	-0.099
0.1050	-0.073	0.3008	-0.123	0.7573	-0.078
0.1532	-0.094	0.3286	-0.126	0.8481	-0.058
0.1942	-0.105	0.3304	-0.127	0.9200	-0.038
0.2106	-0.110	0.3610	-0.131	0.9672	-0.024
0.2211	-0.112	0.3987	-0.132		
318.15 K					
0.0102	-0.009	0.2333	-0.126	0.4131	-0.135
0.0301	-0.031	0.2379	-0.127	0.4379	-0.136
0.0660	-0.058	0.2610	-0.132	0.5151	-0.132
0.0888	-0.076	0.2866	-0.137	0.5322	-0.129
0.1229	-0.092	0.3242	-0.139	0.6153	-0.112
0.1654	-0.108	0.3307	-0.141	0.7250	-0.086
0.1806	-0.112	0.3561	-0.139	0.8015	-0.064
0.1957	-0.120	0.3675	-0.140	0.8813	-0.039
0.2114	-0.123	0.3838	-0.139	0.9514	-0.019

Table 2. Densities, ρ , and viscosities, η , for the binary mixtures at various temperatures

x_1	ρ ($kg \text{ m}^{-3}$)	η ($mPa \text{ s}$)	ρ ($kg \text{ m}^{-3}$)	η ($mPa \text{ s}$)
CH₃(OC₂H₄)OH (1) + C₃H₇OH (2)				
308.15 K				
0.0000	791.29	1.505	783.40	1.232
0.1014	808.0	1.435	800.0	1.168
0.1502	816.0	1.402	808.0	1.142
0.2508	832.4	1.351	824.2	1.089
0.3049	841.2	1.331	832.9	1.079
0.3667	851.2	1.301	842.8	1.062
318.15 K				

Table-2 (contd.)

Table-2 (contd.)

							CH ₃ (OC ₂ H ₄) ₃ OH (1) + C ₃ H ₇ OH (2)						
							298.15 K		308.15 K		318.15 K		
0.4257	860.8	1.303	852.3	1.052									
0.4838	870.1	1.280	861.5	1.036									
0.5161	875.2	1.278	866.7	1.029	0.0000	799.61	1.938	791.29	1.505	783.40	1.232		
0.5378	878.7	1.276	870.1	1.032	0.0134	806.5	1.952	798.1	1.526	790.2	1.246		
0.5647	883.0	1.279	874.4	1.028	0.0366	817.9	1.983	809.5	1.555	801.5	1.273		
0.6129	890.6	1.270	882.0	1.021	0.0639	830.7	2.034	822.2	1.604	814.2	1.320		
0.6700	899.7	1.252	891.0	1.017	0.1165	853.2	2.159	844.6	1.692	836.5	1.400		
0.7387	910.6	1.250	901.8	1.018	0.1568	868.8	2.273	860.2	1.786	852.1	1.484		
0.7685	915.3	1.251	906.4	1.018	0.2037	885.6	2.434	877.0	1.894	868.8	1.576		
0.8213	923.6	1.251	914.7	1.016	0.2664	905.9	2.652	897.2	2.064	889.0	1.715		
0.8898	934.3	1.253	925.3	1.022	0.3205	921.7	2.847	913.0	2.213	904.7	1.851		
0.9239	939.6	1.253	930.6	1.025	0.3498	929.7	3.007	921.0	2.328	912.7	1.927		
0.9491	943.5	1.260	934.6	1.029	0.3669	934.2	3.042	925.5	2.349	917.2	1.973		
0.9574	944.8	1.264	935.8	1.028	0.4076	944.4	3.264	935.8	2.495	927.3	2.085		
0.9686	946.5	1.277	937.5	1.027	0.4623	957.2	3.514	948.5	2.678	940.0	2.228		
0.9871	949.4	1.288	940.4	1.029	0.5601	977.6	4.000	968.9	3.021	960.3	2.510		
1.0000	951.38	1.253	942.39	1.031	0.6022	985.5	4.210	976.8	3.158	968.2	2.624		
CH ₃ (OC ₂ H ₄) ₂ OH (1) + C ₃ H ₇ OH (2)													
							298.15 K		308.15 K		318.15 K		
0.0000	799.61	1.938	791.29	1.505	783.40	1.232	0.7635	1012.2	5.059	1003.5	3.746	994.8	3.074
0.0105	803.2	1.951	794.8	1.522	786.9	1.248	0.8228	1020.7	5.311	1012.0	3.929	1003.3	3.258
0.0278	809.1	1.961	800.6	1.547	792.7	1.250	0.8494	1024.4	5.452	1015.7	4.008	1006.9	3.312
0.0448	814.7	1.966	806.2	1.559	798.2	1.259	0.9137	1032.7	5.740	1024.1	4.230	1015.3	3.489
0.0797	825.9	1.979	817.2	1.566	809.2	1.275	0.9358	1035.5	5.875	1026.8	4.299	1018.0	3.550
0.0978	831.5	1.998	822.8	1.566	814.7	1.280	0.9610	1038.5	6.080	1029.8	4.384	1021.0	3.616
0.1316	841.7	2.020	833.0	1.581	824.8	1.296	1.0000	1043.06	6.287	1034.28	4.535	1025.56	3.726
0.1852	857.1	2.069	848.3	1.613	840.1	1.326							
0.2267	868.5	2.104	859.7	1.648	851.4	1.369							
0.2853	883.7	2.158	874.8	1.693	866.5	1.399							
0.3029	888.1	2.172	879.2	1.713	870.9	1.415							
0.3226	892.9	2.200	884.1	1.724	875.7	1.430							
0.3872	908.1	2.284	899.3	1.790	890.8	1.486							
0.4390	919.6	2.354	910.8	1.840	902.3	1.532							
0.4811	928.6	2.416	919.8	1.888	911.3	1.573							
0.5266	937.9	2.420	929.1	1.940	920.6	1.618							
0.5519	942.9	2.528	934.1	1.969	925.6	1.643							
0.6051	953.1	2.624	944.4	2.037	935.8	1.694							
0.6805	966.8	2.748	958.1	2.138	949.4	1.778							
0.7239	974.3	2.835	965.6	2.193	956.9	1.832							
0.7925	985.6	2.967	977.0	2.290	968.3	1.917							
0.8237	990.6	3.034	981.9	2.338	973.2	1.947							
0.8896	1000.6	3.163	992.0	2.439	983.3	2.027							
0.9096	1003.6	3.207	994.9	2.464	986.3	2.051							
0.9417	1008.2	3.265	999.6	2.509	990.9	2.086							
0.9849	1014.3	3.393	1005.6	2.614	997.0	2.140							
1.0000	1016.43	3.442	1007.7	2.593	999.09	2.159							

viscosities were fitted to a polynomial of the type :

$$\eta = \sum_{i=0} a_i x_i^i \tag{1}$$

by the method of least-squares with each point weighted equally. The values of coefficient a_i and standard deviations σ are listed in Table 3(a). Fig. 1 shows the results of the dynamic viscosity together with the smoothing curves against the mole fraction of the alkoxyethanols at 298.15 K.

The viscosity deviations from a linear dependence on mole fraction average were obtained from relationship :

$$\Delta\eta = \eta - (\eta_1 x_1 + \eta_2 x_2) \tag{2}$$

where η is the dynamic viscosity of the mixtures, and η_1 and η_2 are the viscosities of the pure components 1 and 2, respectively. The uncertainty of the viscosity deviations as calculated is estimated to be less than ± 0.03 mPa s.

The variation of V_m^E and $\Delta\eta$ with composition are expressed by a Redlich-Kister type equation :

Table 3(a). Smoothing coefficients a_i and standard deviations σ of eq. (1) for the binary mixtures at various temperatures

	T/K	a_0	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	σ
$\text{CH}_3(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_4)\text{OH} (1) + \text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH} (2)$							
η (mPa s)	308.15	1.5875	-1.7050	4.0110	-4.6606	2.0557	0.006
	318.15	1.2278	-0.6754	0.6718	-0.1935		0.003
$\text{CH}_3(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_4)_2\text{OH} (1) + \text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH} (2)$							
η (mPa s)	298.15	1.9473	0.3610	1.4279	-0.3265		0.005
	308.15	1.5295	0.3227	0.9608	-0.1939		0.008
	318.15	1.2419	0.3283	0.8874	-0.2988		0.004
$\text{CH}_3(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_4)_3\text{OH} (1) + \text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH} (2)$							
η (mPa s)	298.15	1.9209	1.4744	5.4817	-2.6928		0.028
	308.15	1.5053	1.2546	3.6531	-1.9268		0.009
	318.15	1.2326	1.0627	3.6482	-3.2155	0.9939	0.003

$$Y(x) = x_1 x_2 \sum_{i=0}^4 a_i (x_1 - x_2)^i \quad (3)$$

where a_i the polynomial coefficients. These were obtained by fitting the experimental values to eq. (3) with least-squares methods. The correlated results for the excess volume and the viscosity deviation are given in Table 3(b), together with the standard deviations, σ . Here $Y(x)$ refers to $V_m^E \times 10^6/\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$, or $\Delta\eta/\text{mPa s}$. For all mixtures, $\sigma(V_m^E) \leq 0.003$ for the precision attainable with the dilatometer used.

Fig. 1. Experimental viscosities for $x_2\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH} + x_1\text{CH}_3(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_4)\text{OH}$, (o), ref. 7; $+ x_1\text{CH}_3(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_4)_2\text{OH}$, (Δ); $+ x_1\text{CH}_3(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_4)_3\text{OH}$, (\square), at 298.15 K. Full curves represent the smoothing eq. (1).

The variations of V_m^E and $\Delta\eta$ with the mole fraction of alkoxyethanol at 318.15 K are presented in Figs. 2 and 3, respectively. Fig. 4 shows how the V_m^E s at equimolar composition vary with the size of the polar head group of alkoxyethanol : the excess molar volumes decrease from ethylene glycol monomethyl ether to triethylene glycol

monomethyl ether. It can also be observed that, as the temperature increases, the excess molar volumes also increase in case of ethylene glycol monomethyl ether and diethylene glycol monomethyl ether, and the reverse is the trend in case of triethylene glycol monomethyl ether. The temperature coefficient $(\partial V_m^E/\partial T)_p$ is negative for triethylene glycol monomethyl ether except with ethylene glycol monomethyl ether and diethylene glycol monomethyl ether over the whole mole fraction range. This behavior may be compared with that of the V_m^E of 1-propanol with polyethers⁹, where the excess volumes increase and then decrease with the number of oxygen atom in the ether chain but with increasing of temperature, the excess volumes increase.

The values of volume or thermal expansion coefficients α of the mixtures at a particular composition were calculated for our system by adding the contributions of the expansivities of each component in the mixtures :

$$\alpha = (1/V) [\sum(M_i x_i/\rho_i) \alpha_i + (\partial V_m^E/\partial T)_{p,x}] \quad (4)$$

where ρ_i and α_i are the density and the expansivity of pure component i at any particular temperature, V is the molar volume of the mixture. In Fig. 5, the α plots are shown for different mixtures at 308.15 K in the complete composition range; a diminution of α is observed as the polar head group of alkoxyethanol increases.

Table 2 shows that the viscosities of all these mixtures decrease with increasing temperatures. The absolute values of η for mixtures with 1-propanol molecule at all temperatures vary in the sequence ethylene glycol monomethyl ether < diethylene glycol monomethyl ether < triethylene glycol monomethyl ether. At any particular temperatures, as x_1 increases, the η of ethylene glycol monomethyl ether decreases, whereas for diethylene glycol monomethyl ether and triethylene glycol monomethyl ether it increases. A further comparison of data at different temperatures shows

Table 3(b). Smoothing coefficients a_i and standard deviations σ of eq. (3) for the binary mixtures at various temperatures

CH ₃ (OC ₂ H ₄)OH (1) + C ₃ H ₇ OH (2)						
308.15 K						
$Y(x)$	a_0	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	σ
$V_m^E \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	0.2666	-0.0110	0.0085	-0.0942		0.001
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	-0.3964	0.0983	0.0062	0.1797		0.012
318.15 K						
$V_m^E \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	0.3014	-0.0604	-0.0123	0.0836		0.002
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	-0.3865	0.1102	-0.0381			0.003
CH ₃ (OC ₂ H ₄) ₂ OH (1) + C ₃ H ₇ OH (2)						
298.15 K						
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	-1.0381	0.1514	0.4470	-0.4386	-0.8508	0.015
308.15 K						
$V_m^E \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	-0.0843	0.0060	-0.0623	-0.1135		0.002
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	-0.5691	0.2059	0.1936	-0.3164		0.011
318.15 K						
$V_m^E \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	-0.0341	0.0209	0.0181	-0.0475		0.003
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	-0.4241	0.1288	0.0679	-0.0540		0.005
CH ₃ (OC ₂ H ₄) ₃ OH (1) + C ₃ H ₇ OH (2)						
298.15 K						
$V_m^E \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	-0.4808	0.2368	0.0351	0.1440	-0.3284	0.003
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	-1.6683	1.4134	0.0225	-1.0823	-1.5290	0.020
308.15 K						
$V_m^E \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	-0.5170	0.1888	0.1008	0.0051	-0.5081	0.002
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	-0.8694	0.9939	0.0264	-0.5500	-0.5456	0.007
318.15 K						
$V_m^E \times 10^6$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)	-0.5243	0.2323	-0.1552	0.1430		0.002
$\Delta\eta$ (mPa s)	-0.5703	0.6253	-0.2646	-0.0812		0.003

that the temperature coefficient ($\partial\eta/\partial T$) decreases for the later two mixtures with increase in temperatures.

The $\Delta\eta$ versus composition plot in Fig. 3 shows that deviations in viscosity ($\Delta\eta$) from mole fraction linearity are negative for all the systems at 318.15 K except small positive deviation in lower x_1 for diethylene glycol monomethyl ether + 1-propanol system. In fact, smaller positive deviation for diethylene glycol monomethyl ether + 1-propanol at lower x_1 and for ethylene glycol monomethyl ether + 1-propanol at higher x_1 are observed at 308.15 K. The magnitude of negative deviations increases with increasing polar head group of alkoxyethanol. These sequence, highly related to the strengthening of the cross-

association of these dissimilar molecules with the increase of a -OC₂H₄ group in ethylene glycol monomethyl ether, is also observed for the excess molar volume V_m^E of these mixtures : this behavior may be compared with the V_m^E and $\Delta\eta$ results for mixtures polyethers with 1-propanol : both V_m^E and $\Delta\eta$ increase in positive direction as the polar head group of the polyether increases. Again, the behavior is consistent with that of the V_m^E and $\Delta\eta$ for propylamine + alkoxyethanol⁵ and 1-alkanol¹⁰. As evidenced from the calculations, the viscosity deviations increase with an increase of temperature.

McAllister's multibody interaction model¹¹ was widely used to correlate kinematic viscosity (ν) data. The three-

Fig. 2. Excess molar volumes for $x_2\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH} + x_1\text{CH}_3(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_4)\text{OH}$, (o); $x_1\text{CH}_3(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_4)_2\text{OH}$, (Δ); $x_1\text{CH}_3(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_4)_3\text{OH}$, (\square), at 318.15 K. Full curves represent the smoothing eq. (3).

Fig. 3. Experimental viscosity deviations for $x_2\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH} + x_1\text{CH}_3(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_4)\text{OH}$, (o); $x_1\text{CH}_3(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_4)_2\text{OH}$, (Δ); $x_1\text{CH}_3(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_4)_3\text{OH}$, (\square), at 318.15 K. Full curves represent the smoothing eq. (3).

body McAllister model was defined as

$$\ln v = x_1^3 \ln v_1 + 3x_1^2x_2 \ln Z_{12} + 3x_1x_2^2 \ln Z_{21} + x_2^3 \ln v_2 - \ln [x_1 + x_2 (M_2/M_1)] + 3x_1^2x_2 \ln [(2 + M_2/M_1)/3] + 3x_1x_2^2 \ln [1 + 2 M_2/M_1/3] + x_2^3 \ln (M_2/M_1) \quad (5)$$

and the four-body model was given by

$$\ln v = x_1^4 \ln v_1 + 4x_1^3x_2 \ln Z_{1112} + 6x_1^2x_2^2 \ln Z_{1122} + 4x_1x_2^3 \ln Z_{2221} + x_2^4 \ln v_2 - \ln [x_1 + x_2 (M_2/M_1)] + 4x_1^3x_2 \ln [(3 + M_2/M_1)/4] + 6x_1^2x_2^2 \ln [1 + M_2/M_1/2] + 4x_1x_2^3 \ln [(1 + 3 M_2/M_1)/4] + x_2^4 \ln (M_2/M_1) \quad (6)$$

Fig. 4. Excess molar volumes at $x_1 = 0.5$ for $x_1\text{CH}_3(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_4)_n\text{OH} + x_2\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH}$. (o) 298.15 K; (Δ) 308.15 K; (\square) 318.15 K.

Fig. 5. Isobaric thermal expansivities α at 308.15 K for $x_1\text{CH}_3(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_4)_n\text{OH} + x_2\text{C}_3\text{H}_7\text{OH}$.

where Z_{12} , Z_{21} , Z_{1112} , Z_{1122} and Z_{2221} are interaction parameters and M_i is the molecular mass of pure components i . The correlating ability of eqs. (5–6) was tested by calculating the standard percentage deviation σ (%) between the experimental and the calculated viscosities as

Table 4. Correlated results of McAllister's model

System	T/K	Three-body model			Four-body model			
		v_{12}	v_{21}	AAD%	v_{112}	v_{1122}	v_{2221}	AAD%
CH ₃ (OC ₂ H ₄)OH (1) + C ₃ H ₇ OH (2)	298.15*	1.6026	1.6990	0.22	1.5963	1.8604	1.8436	0.07
	308.15	1.3943	1.4772	0.41	1.3820	1.5849	1.5838	0.34
	318.15	1.1227	1.2076	0.17	1.1128	1.3048	1.2863	0.05
CH ₃ (OC ₂ H ₄) ₂ OH (1) + C ₃ H ₇ OH (2)	298.15	2.8428	2.3898	0.25	2.9474	3.4789	2.3716	0.10
	308.15	2.2471	1.9208	0.43	2.3784	2.6385	1.9446	0.38
	318.15	1.9103	1.6006	0.20	1.9768	2.2925	1.5906	0.09
CH ₃ (OC ₂ H ₄) ₃ OH (1) + C ₃ H ₇ OH (2)	298.15	5.1196	3.0739	1.04	4.8711	6.7262	2.6014	0.19
	308.15	3.8248	2.4673	0.64	3.7336	4.9044	2.1480	0.08
	318.15	3.1710	2.1191	0.63	3.1017	4.1217	1.8316	0.04

*Calculated from Ref. 7.

$$\text{AAD}(\%) = [1 / (n - k) \sum (100 (v_{\text{exp}} - v_{\text{cal}}) / v_{\text{exp}})^2]^{1/2} \quad (7)$$

where n represents the number of experimental points and k the number of numerical coefficients in the eqs. (5–6).

The values of the different parameters and the percentage standard deviations are given in Table 4. The average deviations are about within the experimental uncertainty, regardless of the four-body or the three-body model being used.

Furthermore, it is useful to discuss the activation parameter of viscous flow, which is defined by the viscosity equation proposed by Eyring and co-workers¹²:

$$\eta = (hN/V) \exp(\Delta G^* / RT) \quad (8)$$

$$\text{combined with } \Delta G^* = \Delta H^* - T\Delta S^* \quad (9)$$

yields the equation

$$R \ln(\eta V) = [R \ln h N - \Delta S^*] + \Delta H^* / T \quad (10)$$

where h is Planck's constant, N is the Avogadro number, ΔH^* is the enthalpy of activation for viscous flow, and ΔS^* is the entropy. A plot of $R \ln(\eta V)$ versus $1/T$ for each binary mixture were found to be linear, indicating that the ΔH^* values are constant in the temperature range 298.15 to 318.15 K. The ΔS^* and ΔH^* values vary from 8 to 1 J mol⁻¹ K⁻¹ and 16 to 20 kJ mol⁻¹ for all the mixtures. It was found that the values of ΔH^* are positive and increase with the mole fraction of the ether except with ethylene glycol monomethyl ether. This indicates that the formation of activation complex necessary for viscous flow appears quite easy in the 1-propanol-rich region and become difficult as the ether concentration increases. The positive value of ΔS^* are found to decrease as the mole fraction of the ether in the mixture increases. This suggests that in initial state, during viscous flow, the liquid is more structured as a result of the formation of the activated species. The high positive value of ΔS^* of triethylene glycol monomethyl ether or

diethylene glycol monomethyl ether + 1-propanol are indicative of the randomness in the solution; this results in higher viscosities and lower negative excess volume for triethylene glycol monomethyl ether. That is, the motion of molecules in the mixtures is less leading to specific interactions between unlike molecules. These results also supports the conclusion drawn from the absolute values of $\Delta\eta$ and V_m^E .

Experimental

1-Propanol (S.R.L., Mumbai, GC 99.5%), and ethylene glycol monomethyl ether (S.D. Fine Chemicals, A.R., GC 99.5%) were dried over ferrous sulphate (A.R., B.D.H.) and then fractionally distilled under reduced nitrogen gas pressure as described elsewhere^{13,14}. Diethylene glycol monomethyl ether (Merck-Schuchardt, FRG, GC >98%), and triethylene glycol monomethyl ether (Fluka; puram, GC >97%) were used without further purification. Prior to measurements, however, all liquids were degassed and dried over Fluka type 4 nm molecular sieves. The purity of the liquids were checked by measuring and comparing the density and viscosity at 298.15 ± 0.01 K and atmospheric pressure with the corresponding literature values.

Densities of pure solvents were measured with a single-arm pycnometer. The pycnometer was calibrated at the working temperatures with doubly distilled water. The sensitivity of the pycnometer corresponded to a precision in density of 1×10^{-3} kg m⁻³. The reproducibility of the density measurements was found to be within 3×10^{-2} kg m⁻³. 1-Propanol, ethylene glycol monomethyl ether, diethylene glycol monomethyl ether and triethylene glycol monomethyl ether at 298.15 K had densities of 799.61 [lit. 799.60 (ref. 14); 799.58 (ref. 15); 799.59 (ref. 16)]; 960.32 [lit. 960.24 (ref. 14); 960.20 (ref. 19)]; 1016.43 [lit. 1016.7 (ref. 14); 1015.91 (ref. 21)]; 1043.06 [lit. 1043.10 (ref. 22);

1045.24 (ref. 23)] kg m⁻³ and viscosities of 1.938 [lit. 1.9430 (ref. 14); 1.943 (ref. 17); 1.9429 (ref. 18)]; 1.534 [lit. 1.60 (ref. 14); 1.5414 (ref. 20)]; 3.442 [lit. 3.480 (ref. 14)]; 6.287 [lit. 6.253 (ref. 23)] mPa s.

Excess molar volumes, reproducible to $\pm 0.003 \times 10^{-6}$ m³ mol⁻¹, were measured directly with a continuous dilution dilatometer similar to that described by Dickinson *et al.*²⁴. Details of its calibration, experimental setup, and measuring procedures have been described previously^{25,26}. The mole fraction of each mixture was obtained with an uncertainty of 1×10^{-4} from the measured mass of one of the components. All masses were corrected for buoyancy. Conversions to molar quantities were based on the relative atomic mass table of 1985 issued by IUPAC²⁷.

The kinematic viscosities ($\nu = \eta/\rho$) of both the pure liquids and liquid mixtures were measured at (298.15, 308.15, and 318.15) K and atmospheric pressure using an Ubbelohde suspended-level viscometer²⁸.

The viscometer was calibrated so as to determine the two constants *A* and *B* in the equation $\eta = \rho (At - B/t)$, obtained by measuring the flow time with thrice-distilled water and twice-distilled cyclohexane¹⁴ and 2-propanol²⁹ and without distill solvents like diethylene glycol diethylether³⁰ and dipropylene glycol monobutyl ether³¹ and 2-propylene carbonate²¹ at the working temperatures. The viscometer is filled with liquid or liquids mixtures, and its limbs are closed with Teflon caps, taking due precaution to minimize the evaporation losses. The details of the apparatus and procedures have been described previously^{32,33}. The flow-time measurements were made using an electronic stopwatch with a precision of ± 0.01 s. An average of four or five set of flow times were taken for each liquid or liquid mixtures. The caps of the limbs are removed during the measurements of flow time. The measured values of the kinematic viscosities (ν) were converted to dynamic viscosities (η) after multiplication by the density. The reproducibility of viscosity results was found to be ± 0.003 mPa s. A thermostatically controlled, well-stirred water bath whose temperature was controlled to ± 0.01 K was used for all the measurements. Densities of liquid mixtures were computed from the excess molar volume and composition according to the relation :

$$\rho = (x_1 M_1 + x_2 M_2) / (V_m^E + x_1 V_1 + x_2 V_2) \quad (11)$$

where x_1 and x_2 are mole fractions, and V_1 and V_2 are molar volumes of alkoxyethanols (1) and 1-propanol (2), respectively. The accuracy in ρ due to the estimated accuracy in excess molar volume ($\pm 0.003 \times 10^{-6}$ m³ mol⁻¹) is 1×10^{-1}

kg m⁻³.

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